

Focus Area: Geodetic Space Weather Research

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Present Status and Progress

The following items should be mentioned here:

- The EGU General Assembly 2022, the first-ever fully hybrid EGU meeting, was taking place in Vienna, Austria and online from May 23 to May 27, 2022. The Session G5.1 “Ionosphere, thermosphere and space weather: monitoring and modelling” within the Geodesy Division was partly dedicated to the topics of the FA-GSWR. The convener of the session was Ehsan Forootan, Michael Schmidt a co-convener. The session included in total 15 Pico presentations on the topics of ionosphere and thermosphere.
- The 2nd IAG Commission 4 Symposium took place as a hybrid meeting from September 5 to September 8, 2022 in Potsdam, Germany (<https://iag-commission4-symposium2022.net/>). This symposium was carried out in close cooperation with the IGS and in particular with the FA-GSWR. The Session S9 chaired by Ehsan Forootan (online), Michael Schmidt (in person) and Stefan Lotz (member of IAGA, online), included 8 oral presentation (3 invited talks) and was filling almost one day of the conference programme. During the conference two splinter meetings have been organized:
 - A joint splinter meeting of the IAG Commission 4: Positioning and Applications, Sub-Commission 4.3: Atmosphere Remote Sensing (SC 4.3) and the GGOS Focus Area: Geodetic Space Weather Research (FA-GSWR) took place at Monday, September 5. Amongst other topics, the current status of each of the Study and Working Groups as well of each of the Joint Study and Joint Working Groups related to the SC 4.3 and the FA-GSWR have been presented and discussed.
 - On Thursday, September 8, a splinter meeting of members of the IAG and the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA) took place on future collaborations. Indeed, the IAGA hosts an Interdivisional Commission on Space Weather (IDC-SW) chaired by Stefan Lots (South African National Space Agency) and Laure Lefevre (Royal Observatory of Belgium, ROB), which deals with similar topics as the FA-GSWR. Consequently, a discussion about a close cooperation between IAG and IAGA seems purposeful. According to the IUGG, in order to set up a Joint Study Group (JSG) or Joint Working Group (JWG) of IAG and IAGA members, the "Terms of Reference", i.e. a description of the topic and the objectives, must be presented and the formal structure and working methods of the group must be defined. It was therefore proposed that such a group be established at the 2023

IUGG meeting with a "Terms of Reference" document. A corresponding proposal must then be approved by the responsible persons.

- Setup of the session “Ionosphere, thermosphere and space weather: monitoring and modelling” in the preliminary program of the Geodesy Division at the EGU 2023 General Assembly from 23 to 28 April, 2023. At the moment, this Status Report is written, the format of the EGU 2023 is not finally decided, but will be announced in November 2022. Like in the last years the session “Ionosphere, thermosphere and space weather: monitoring and modelling” will be installed as a Pico session and partly dedicated to the topics of the FA-GSWR. Abstracts can be submitted between November 1, 2022 and January 10, 2023, 13:00 CET. The convener of the session will be Ehsan Forootan; Michael Schmidt, Claudia Borries, Kristin Vielberg, and Mona Kosary will act as co-conveners.
- The official scientific programme of the 28th General Assembly of the IUGG in Berlin from 11 to 20 July 2023 has been prepared over the last months and is now available on the website <https://www.iugg2023berlin.org/>. Several sessions will be dedicated to Geodetic Remote Sensing including Atmospheric Modelling and Space Weather Research. The most important one from the FA-GSWR perspective is the Symposium JG03: Remote Sensing and Modelling of the Atmosphere, involving the associations IAG, IAGA, IAMAS and IAVCEI. The convener of this symposium is Michael Schmidt (IAG); the co-conveners are Ehsan Forootan (Denmark, IAG), Loren Chang (Taiwan, IAGA), Claudia Stubenrauch (France, IAMAS) and Fabio Dioguardi (Italy, IAVCEI).
- Based on the results of the Fifth National Space Weather Workshop held from 21 to 23 September, 2021, online, a document was prepared by the German space weather expert community (e.g. from BKG, DLR Neustrelitz, DLR Bonn, GFZ, DGFI-TUM) that includes recommendations for enhancing the German space weather capabilities and capacities in a coordinated approach. This 13-page document – written in German – is officially addressed to the German Federal Government.
- The structure of the FA-GSWR comprises one GGOS Joint Study Group (JSG), associated with the Inter-Commission Committee on Theory (ICCT) of the IAG and denoted as ICCT-JSG T 0.27, and three Joint Working Groups (JWG), directly associated with the FA-GSWR.
- The following ‘Present Activities’ and ‘Future Plans’ of the JSG and the JWGs of the FA-GSWR are worth mentioning:

JSG 1 (ICCT-JSG 0.27): Coupling processes between magnetosphere, thermosphere and ionosphere; Chair: Andres Calabia Aibar (China), Vice-Chair: Munawar Shah (Pakistan), Research Coordinator: Binod Adhikari (Nepal), 17 group members

Present activities:

- Relaunch in November 2021 of special Issue "Advances on upper-atmosphere characterization for geodetic space weather research and applications", in *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*
- Collaboration Scheme with the Low Latitude Ionospheric Research Working Group of the Asia Oceania Society of Geosciences (AOGS - Regional Advisory Committee)
- Collaboration Scheme with Young Earth System Scientists (YESS) community for seminars, cooperation, etc.
- Cooperate and finish existing projects; elaboration of new proposals.

- Interactions with the other groups of the Focus Area Geodetic Space Weather Research, selected IAG Commissions, etc.

Future plans:

- Elaboration of a proposal for an International Workshop on MTI Coupling (IWMTIC2023): Prospects, Challenges, and Opportunities. Kathmandu, Nepal.
- Advancement of MTI sciences in developing countries by organizing workshops, etc.
- Keeping the Website-Forum in Research Gate active and updated.
- Submission of new SCI papers, conference proceedings, projects, etc.

JWG 1: Electron density modelling; Chair: Fabricio dos Santos Prol (Finland), Vice-Chair: Alberto Garcia-Rigo (Spain), 18 group members

Present work:

- Creating an extensive simulation scenario to perform a 3D model validation with a known ionosphere-plasmasphere system
- Creating a study case of the plasmasphere

Future plans:

- Evaluation of the 3D models using data from the simulated scenario
- Evaluation of the plasmasphere models

JWG 2: Improvement of thermosphere models; Chair: Christian Siemes (The Netherlands), Vice-Chair: Kristin Vielberg (Germany), 9 group members

Present work:

- Comparison of models and data for the GRACE A satellite (calibration, radiation pressure and aerodynamic modelling)
- New density datasets from the GRACE and GRACE-FO mission

Future plans:

- GNSS-derived mass density observations
- SLR-derived mass density observations

JWG 3: Improved understanding of space weather events and their monitoring by satellite missions; Chair: Haixia Lyu (China) Vice-Chair: Benedikt Soja (Switzerland), 11 group members

Present work:

- Analysis of the correlation between SW products and perturbed ionospheric electron density/TEC
- Identification of the main parameters that could be useful to improve real time determination as well as the prediction of ionospheric/plasmaspheric TEC and electron density estimates, in case of extreme solar weather conditions

Future plans:

- Improving the near real-time (NRT) and real-time (RT) determination of the electron density within the ionosphere and plasmasphere to detect space weather events in collaboration with JWG1
 - Combination of measurements and estimates derived from space geodetic observation techniques and from solar spacecraft missions by conducting extensive simulations, combining different data sets and testing different algorithms.
 - Comparison and validation using external data, in particular data from spacecrafts.
- During the Corona pandemic and the related lockdowns many papers have been written in the reporting period on topics related to the JSG and the JWGs of the FA-GSWR.
 - In the same manner significant progress has been made in third-party funded national and international projects, which are often strongly coupled to the objectives of the JGS and the JWGs of the FA-GSWR.

Planned Actions and Milestones

- Continuation of the work on the definition and selection of the essential geodetic variables (EGV) in the framework of the scientific work within FA-GSWR.
- Planning of a splinter meetings of the FA-GSWR during the EGU GA 2023 in Vienna and during the 28th General Assembly of the IUGG in Berlin.
- Reformulation of the 'Terms of Reference' according to the outcome of the two splinter meetings listed before.
- Christian Siemes as the chair of the JSG 2 will step down next year. Consequently, a candidate needs to be find and installed.
- As already mentioned above a JSG or a JWG of IAG and IAGA members should be established. Following the statutes of IUGG, IAG and IAGA. A corresponding meeting of IAG and IAGA members should be scheduled for the IUGG 2023 General Assembly in Berlin.